

Eluxevo:

Navigating open source and AI
within complex energy systems

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THE ALAN TURING INSTITUTE CASE STUDY

Eluxevo:

Navigating open source and AI within complex energy systems

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Topic overview

This case study explores how **Eluxevo**, a UK-based startup, is developing AI-enabled solutions to improve energy efficiency and thermal comfort in our homes. Founded by Maximillian (Max) Smith, the company sits at the intersection of energy systems, human behaviour and AI. A central strategic question for Eluxevo concerns the role of open source: how can it accelerate innovation that can address the barriers faced by a broad range of stakeholders, and reduce barriers to entry? And what are the tensions around intellectual property, revenue generation and long-term sustainability? Participation in The Turing Way Practitioners Hub has influenced Eluxevo's thinking in areas including risk, governance, stakeholder mapping, and responsible AI implementation.

The thermostat problem

For Max, the starting point is a deceptively simple question: why does a technology as important as the thermostat remain fundamentally unchanged for decades, despite the increasing complexity of modern energy systems?

The complicated answer is because it is layered with technical, regulatory, behavioural and commercial “pluralities”. Heating systems, for example, operate according to laws of physics and thermodynamics, whereas end users experience comfort in subjective and emotional ways. This creates a structural tension, says Max, in which people are at the mercy of a dial or digital interface that hides an opaque system remote from the lived reality of cost, sustainability and wellbeing.

In a world where energy prices fluctuate and **many households experience fuel poverty**, Max believes that the traditional ‘thermostat to control air temperature’ model is no longer fit for purpose. Eluxevo’s ambition is to use AI-integrated hardware to make our home heating and lighting systems more responsive and adaptive, helping to increase both affordability and sustainability.

AI-enabled comfort and energy optimisation

Eluxevo is developing machine learning software designed to optimise thermal comfort in buildings while reducing energy waste and carbon impact. The company’s patent-pending Adaptive Personal Comfort System (APeCS) builds on several rounds of Innovate UK funding, which supported early-stage system-centred and user-centred design processes that follow the **‘double diamond’ approach**. The result is an intuitive user interface linked to innovative technology that combines machine learning and automation elements with infrared heating, ventilation, smart lighting and indoor sensors.

This combination simulates the feeling of sunshine, which improves the experience of warmth in cooler air temperatures, while light is also an important component in enhancing mental wellbeing. It is energy-intensive to heat water, to heat air, and to then heat people and things. Infrared heats people directly, and Eluxevo’s system heats where it is needed to just the right amount. This offers significant energy demand reduction and flexibility over the traditional thermostat.

But Eluxevo's value proposition extends beyond comfort and bills. Max notes that on one hand, affluent homeowners may “set and forget” heating schedules and waste energy overheating empty spaces. This drives up demand and the cost of energy supply for all. On the other, the most vulnerable in society often live in poorly heated homes, driven by occupant anxiety over affordability. This can contribute to cold-related illnesses and places additional burden on public services such as the NHS. Improving heating efficiency can therefore be seen as a public health and social equality intervention, as well as a cost-saving or carbon-reduction measure.

The core challenge for the company lies in reconciling the two variable systems at play: the physical energy system (governed by thermodynamics, infrastructure constraints, and the broader energy market), and the human system (defined by comfort preferences, financial pressures, and behavioural patterns). AI is intended to help model the complex relationships between these interacting variables, and to do so effectively requires access to large volumes of real-world data from what Max describes as “living labs” – real homes and offices, across a range of demographic contexts. Models are pre-trained and then deployed and retrained over time (there is, acknowledges Max, a “chicken-and-egg” dynamic here: proper training requires real deployments, yet deployments require validated models).

Open-source tools in a complex ecosystem: opportunities and challenges

The open-source community has played a key role in Eluxevo's development. As a startup working with limited resources, the company has relied heavily on open-source technologies such as Linux operating systems, Python programming environments, and modelling tools such as **Blender** and **OpenFOAM** to prototype physics and train AI systems. Open-source interoperability protocols like **MQTT**, **Thread** and **Zigbee** have also emerged in the Internet-of-Things space, enabling communication between devices such as thermostats and sensors.

Making use of open source in this way, says Max, lowers barriers to entry. It enables small teams with innovative ideas to translate them into tangible systems without prohibitive licensing costs or being locked out by proprietary ecosystems. The UK research university ecosystem has further supported this grassroots innovation, helping to “bring the outside in” through academic collaboration and open research – including Eluxevo's participation in the Practitioners Hub community.

“Innovation comes from that cross-pollination,” says Max. “It doesn’t exist in silos. When you think in systems, you realise that this isn’t just about a single piece of software. In our context, it’s about the user – the human part of any technical solution – and how they interact with energy companies, regulation, pricing structures and so on. Open source enables innovation because it allows value to be shared and barriers to be lowered. But at the same time, it comes into direct contrast and friction with the capitalist parts of the system that are pushing for growth, proprietary control and revenue protection. That tension is very real.”

Operating as a “lean” startup, the team experienced software affordability barriers and challenges in accessing data to pilot-test system integrations in a proof-of-concept approach designed to attract investment to address system failures. Moreover, unlocking investment comes with a risk-adjustment, which may see the development of open source as diluting returns.

Eluxevo must therefore consider how to balance what Max sees as a responsibility to “give back” to the open source community (to encourage innovation in the ecosystem of opportunity that they are creating) with an equally strong imperative to protect intellectual property, maintain revenue streams, and create economic growth. In the UK context, where tech funding is competitive and often risk-averse, early decisions about openness may affect investors’ views of a venture’s long-term viability and profitability. On one hand, there are the resources required to maintain a safe, secure and reliable open-source ecosystem. This may be seen by investors as a “distraction” from the focus on efficient revenue generation. On the other hand are the emergent co-created opportunities that foster innovation for multiple parties and applications, which may not otherwise be identified or possible to action.

Max is also – in large part thanks to Practitioners’ Hub sessions – acutely aware of the legal and governance ambiguities surrounding open source in AI contexts. Questions of data and model ownership, security, maintenance and responsibility are in flux – what Max perceives as a concerning “wild west” environment in parts of the AI landscape. If a public or private organisation relies on open-source systems that later become compromised, unsustainable or unsupported, the consequences could be significant, although the same is also true for proprietary software. Practitioners Hub discussions around open source, legal risk, stakeholder mapping and data security have helped clarify the need for robust governance – and to decide who is responsible for that governance – around Eluxevo’s open-influenced, AI-enabled systems.

Navigating the open source ecosystem

Getting started in the open source ecosystem for Eluxevo depended on a blend of team experience and personal pointers from trusted sources such as the Practitioners' Hub. However, for any start-ups or small businesses considering incorporating open source into their technical stack but are unsure where to start, **The Open Source Initiative (OSI)** is a not-for-profit that supports institutions and individuals worldwide working on best practice in open source and other resources such as how to approach **data governance in open source AI**. **OpenUK**, another expert community, also produces up-to-date coverage of key issues around open source. Initiatives such as **OpenChain** also provide the infrastructure for security assurance and **software bills of materials**, a documentation standard growing in popularity across industries. Finally, if an organisation is looking to leverage open models, datasets, or weights, the **Hugging Face platform** hosts +15,000 models under a variety of open or permissive licenses.

Next steps: From innovation to adoption

Eluxevo now enters a critical phase in its evolution: moving from research and grant-supported development towards commercial growth. This will require a continued funding pipeline to sustain operations while also demonstrating sufficient maturity and impact (through real-world pilot deployments) to attract further investment. It also requires balancing technical advancement and value chain collaboration with speed of execution: waiting for a flawless system to emerge may delay a route to market. A risk-averse market, formed through established beliefs, social norms and practices, is hesitant to engage with an ecosystem of unfamiliar innovation that appears inherently riskier.

Strengthening cyber security capabilities through the National Cyber Security Centre and aligning with the British Standards Institution on policy and governance form part of this preparation – particularly important with supply chain partners and stakeholders that may be cautious about AI integration and open-source technologies. Amid a growing recognition that both AI and open-source technologies can and do democratise the capability for complex problems to be solved, Max is committed to building his teams’ capabilities in-house where possible (for example, using AI to assist with software development). But he also recognises that engaging external expertise is essential in certain key areas, where resources permit and where they are not blocked by vested interests. “These areas are linked and increase in complexity the more you unpack the details of systems and stakeholders,” adds Max. “Managing open source requires maintenance and governance including, for example, licensing expertise, data security and cyber security. Who is responsible when systems misperform with serious repercussions, and what risk is acceptable?”

He adds: “How innovation gets from idea stage to adoption is fundamentally critical. That’s what we’re focused on now as a company. We are making every effort to engage with external centres of excellence to help us uncover the unknowns and learn from the experts and the journeys of other innovators – but perfection can be the enemy of good. We need to evidence the benefit of our innovation, building trust by reducing risks in a measured and timely way.”

Reflections on *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub

“The Practitioners Hub has been incredibly helpful in supporting me to apply a critical lens to how we look at open source, and the implementation and impact of AI. The open source session in particular highlighted just how complex the legal and governance landscape is: there are questions around data ownership, model ownership, IP, and long-term responsibility. If you’re not careful, you can bake future risk into a system from day one. What I appreciated about the Hub is that it’s well curated, and I enjoyed having both in-person and online exchanges with other innovators from different sectors about best practices in areas such as stakeholder mapping.”

Maximillian Smith,
Founder and Director of Eluxevo

Key takeaways

- AI (including machine learning techniques) can be employed in the home heating sector to reconcile the complexities of energy systems and infrastructure with human comfort and affordability.
- Making use of open-source software can lower barriers to innovation – especially for resource-conscious startups. But it can also introduce strategic tensions and trade-offs around IP, commercial revenue and governance that need to be properly understood at an early stage.
- One major challenge for companies looking to build real-world systems is the need for data to train and validate the models used, which is only possible to generate once the systems are deployed. “Living labs” and trial periods can help meet this challenge.
- Utilising a variety of different external expertise sources can help build up a robust picture of different aspects of business, product, and supply chain considerations, such as cybersecurity and data governance.
- Innovation rarely happens in silos, cannot happen through closed doors, and often finds its most fertile ground in open research, development and discussion communities, where problems are identified by personal realities, and solutions are developed that benefit wider needs.

Contributors and acknowledgements

This case study is published under *The Turing Way Practitioners Hub* 2025-26 Cohort – case study series. The Practitioners Hub is *The Turing Way* project that works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2025, The Turing Way team welcomed **Max Smith from Eluxevo** as an Expert-in-Residence to discuss and share their implementation approaches to data science and AI, as well as build additional skills around best practices in responsible, ethical, and collaborative working. We thank them for leading the development of this case study.

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency, and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

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The Turing Way Practitioners Hub's 2025-26 Cohort was co-delivered by **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher – Open Source Practices and Dr Ann Borda, Senior Research Community Manager. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical writer for this case study, and others in the series. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager and **Dr Ann Borda** is the Case Study Liaison for this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Malvika Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

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